

FREEDAM CONNECTIONS: CONCEPTION, TESTING AND BEHAVIOUR UNDER SEISMIC ACTIONS

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SUMMARY: *This paper is devoted to a brief presentation of the main results obtained within the FREEDAM research project. The project has been completed and, recently, also the dissemination of the results has reached the finish line. The project was devoted to the development of low-damage beam-to-column connections based on the use of friction dampers conceived to substitute the traditional dissipative zones of moment-resisting frames, i.e. the beam ends. The conception of these innovative connections is presented and the experimental tests carried out at the University of Salerno during the FREEDAM project are summarized dealing with the friction dampers, the beam-to-column joints sub-assemblages and the seismic simulation of a real scale one-bay two-storey building with the pseudo-dynamic testing method. Finally, the design procedures for seismic-resistant steel frames equipped with such connections are presented in the framework of Eurocode 8 and according to TPMC.*

KEYWORDS: *friction dampers, beam-to-column connections, low-damage, steel structures, failure mode control*

1 Introduction

The research project FREEDAM, the acronym of “FREE from DAMage steel connections”, was co-financed by the European Union Research Fund for Coal and Steel following the RFCS Call 2015. The FREEDAM project was aimed at the development of a new design strategy whose goal is the design of connections able to withstand without any damage the rotation demands due to destructive seismic events. Such innovative beam-to-column connections are equipped with friction dampers which are located at the bottom flange level of the connected beam to dissipate the earthquake input energy. The friction resistance is calibrated by acting on the number and the diameter of the bolts and their tightening torque governing the preloading. The flexural resistance results from the product between the damper friction resistance and the lever arm. The connections are conceived to exhibit wide and stable hysteresis loops without any damage to the connection steel plate elements. Therefore, the basic idea of the work was inspired by the strategy of supplementary energy dissipation, but it is based on the use of damping devices from a new perspective. While passive control strategies have been commonly based on the integration of the energy dissipation capacity of the primary structure using a supplementary dissipation coming from damping devices, conversely, the FREEDAM design strategy is based on the use of friction dampers conceived in such a way to substitute the traditional dissipative zones of moment-resisting frames, i.e. the beam ends. The development of the FREEDAM connections has to be considered, on one hand, a first

important goal because of the benefits coming from the elimination of the connection repair costs in the aftermath of a destructive seismic event and, on the other hand, a step towards the ambitious goal of free from damage buildings which will require, additionally, the identification of connection details, between the non-structural components and the primary structure, able to prevent also the damage to non-structural components (cladding panels, ceilings, plant facilities, etc.) and systems.

The FREEDAM project involved 6 partners, including 4 universities and 2 industrial partners:

- the University of Salerno (Italy), as project coordinator, coordinated by Prof. V. Piluso;
- the University of Liege (Belgium), coordinated by Prof. Jean-Pierre Jaspart;
- the University of Naples “Federico II” (Italy), coordinated by Prof. Raffaele Landolfo;
- the University of Coimbra (Portugal), coordinated by Prof. Luis Simoes Da Silva;
- FIP Industriale S.p.A. (Italy), coordinated by Dr. Eng. Maria Gabriella Castellano;
- O Feliz Metalomecanica S.A. (Portugal), coordinated by Dr. Eng. José Manuel Silva.

The European dimension of the research consortium allowed the execution of a wide experimental campaign concerning the friction dampers, beam-to-column sub-assemblages and the seismic testing of a two-storey building. In particular, 120 experimental tests on friction dampers subjected to cyclic loading conditions (60 under low-velocity conditions and 60 under high-velocity conditions, including loading histories simulating real earthquakes) were carried out for investigating the tribological properties of different coating procedures for realizing the friction pads of the dampers. In addition, the friction dampers were also subjected to 6 tests under impact loading, as a preliminary study concerning structural robustness, and to 6 long-term tests aimed to investigate the bolt preloading losses occurring during the life-cycle of the structure. The cyclic behaviour of beam-to-column connections equipped with friction dampers was investigated by performing 8 experimental tests on external beam-to-column connections and 8 tests on internal beam-to-column connections. Moreover, 6 experimental tests on beam-to-column connections subjected to impact loading were carried out to get important information for exceptional loading conditions requiring structural robustness. Finally, 10 seismic simulations on a two-storey building were performed using the pseudo-dynamic testing method. In particular, 5 earthquake simulations concerned the building equipped with traditional connections and 5 simulations regarded the same building but equipped with FREEDAM connections. The comparison between the obtained displacement time histories and the structural damage occurring in the case of the building specimens equipped with traditional connections pointed out the advantages of FREEDAM connections that behaved according to the free from damage design goal.

All the experimental tests were accompanied by advanced numerical simulations. In particular, the blind predictions of the cyclic response of the FREEDAM connections, carried out by advanced FE models, resulted in a very good agreement with the successive experimental observations. All these research efforts have been described in a book recently published by ECCS [Piluso et al., 2022] which is one of the main outcomes of the FREEDAM-PLUS Project. The FREEDAM-PLUS project (“Valorisation of knowledge for FREE from DAMAGE steel connections”) was also funded by the European Union Research Fund for Coal and Steel, following the RFCS Call 2019, to disseminate the main results of the FREEDAM project.

This paper is devoted to a concise presentation of the conception of FREEDAM connections and the wide experimental work carried out at the University of Salerno during the project development. In particular, the experimental response of FREEDAM friction dampers under cyclic loading conditions is described with the criteria adopted for the definition and the

evaluation of the tribological properties needed for the connection design and the modelling of their behaviour under seismic actions. Moreover, the main results of the experimental tests carried out on beam-to-column joint sub-assemblages are presented. Furthermore, the experimental results of seismic simulations performed by the pseudo-dynamic testing method are presented.

Finally, the procedures for the seismic design of moment-resisting frames equipped with FREEDAM connections are briefly presented, both in the framework of Eurocode 8 and according to the Theory of Plastic Mechanism Control (TPMC) [Mazzolani and Piluso, 1997; Montuori, Nastri, Piluso, 2015].

2 Investigations on friction materials

2.1 Friction materials studied during the FREEDAM project

This paragraph deals with the studies conducted at the University of Salerno for selecting friction materials suitable for application in FREEDAM joints. The properties of the friction interface of a seismic damper, in general, need to address two main objectives. On the one hand, high friction coefficient values are required to reduce the number of bolts and, consequently, the size of the dampers. On the other hand, the reduction of wearing is also significant because it limits the loss of bolt preloading and the corresponding progressive reduction of the slip resistance. To satisfy both requirements, many tests have been carried out at the University of Salerno since 2010, with investigations extended to several friction materials whose properties have been deeply examined with cyclic tests on lap-shear joints.

The friction coefficient (μ) of an interface is typically dependent on the ratio between the critical shear stress of the weakest material (s_0) and the hardness of the softest material (σ_0) in contact [Bowden and Tabor, 1950]. This principle highlights that high friction coefficients can be obtained with relatively high-strength materials and only if a significant difference in the superficial hardness characterises the friction interface. The friction dampers of FREEDAM joints are constituted by internal stainless steel plates made of 1.4301 grade (equivalent to AISI 304), with a superficial hardness equal to 130 HV. Considering this reference hardness, five relatively soft metals (labelled from M1 to M5, with hardness ranging between 5 HV and 30 HV), applied in the form of coating materials, and three hard materials, consisting of two carbide alloys and a diamond powder (labelled from M6 to M8, with a hardness varying between 550 HV and 1200 HV), have been tested.

Depending on the superficial hardness of the materials in one case (hard materials), the consumption of the steel plate is promoted. In this case, the friction coefficient depends mainly on the steel plate's shear resistance and superficial hardness ratio. Conversely, in the case of soft materials, the consumption of the shims is observed, and the friction coefficient depends mainly on the mechanical properties of the coating material itself.

2.2 Cyclic response of the selected materials

During the FREEDAM project, 63 low-speed and 60 high-speed cyclic tests were performed to characterise the friction dampers' slip properties. The studies focused on the features that affect the friction pads' response: i) the type of friction material; ii) the bolts' preload; iii) the random material variability; iv) the loading speed. The tests on the coating materials are aimed

For some hard materials, the hysteretic curves were affected by an initial stick and slip phase inducing a first unstable cycle. This phenomenon probably depends on the high difference between the static and kinetic value of the friction coefficient. Figure 2 (left) shows the results for the shims coated with M6 material. Figure 2 (right) clarifies that since M6 is a hard material, many scratches were generated on the stainless steel plate. During the tests with the hard materials, the bolts lost about 7% of their initial preload after the first cycle, with a total loss at the end of the tests of about 20%.

Materials M1 and M4 also exhibited a behaviour characterised by broad and stable cycles (Figure 3, left). Nevertheless, for these materials, the reduction of the friction coefficient was more significant due to both damage to the friction pads and the reduction of bolts' preloading. When the maximum preloading force was applied, the degradation of the slippage force was equal to about 50% for the soft materials. The friction coefficients ranged between 0.55 and 0.65 for material M1 and 0.7 and 0.9 for material M4. In these cases, it was possible to observe that wearing was concentrated mainly in the friction shims (Figure 3, right). Figure 4 shows the influence of preloading forces ranging between 70% (left) and 40% (right) of the proof preload on the hysteretic response of material M4. This figure highlights that the degradation reduces as far as the bolt preloading force is reduced. The large number of tests executed during the FREEDAM project has permitted identifying standardised values of the friction coefficients.

Figure 4 – Influence of the bolts' preload on the force-displacement hysteretic response (material M4)

Specifically, the investigations have allowed defining three values of the friction coefficient to be used for: i) the check of the non-slip condition at both serviceability and ultimate limit states, ii) the resistance of the FREEDAM joints for the seismic situation, iii) the design of the non-dissipative structural components considering the overstrength exhibited by the friction devices. The obtained design values are summarised in Table 1 for material M4, which is the material that was proposed during the FREEDAM project for application in friction joints. More details concerning the test presented in this section are reported in [Ferrante Cavallaro *et al.*, 2017, 2018a,b; Santos *et al.*, 2020; D'Antimo *et al.*, 2020]. The problem of calibrating partial safety factors to be used for different design requirements has been also investigated using a probabilistic approach [Di Lauro *et al.*, 2019].

Table 1 – Statistical values of the friction coefficients for design purposes

<i>Design FC</i>	μ
Static 5% fractile	0.69
Static 95% fractile	0.84
Dynamic 5% fractile	0.53

3 Experimental tests on beam-to-column sub-assemblies

To establish the performance of FREEDAM joints under cyclic loads, eight cyclic tests on external beam-to-column connections have been performed at the STRENGTH laboratory of the University of Salerno [Latour *et al.*, 2013, 2015, 2018a, 2018b]. Two different geometrical configurations have been conceived and tested (Figure 5): with the damper parallel to the beam flanges (HFC), namely horizontal configuration, and with the damper parallel to the beam web (VFC), namely vertical configuration. In the tests, both IPE270 and IPE450 beam profiles have been considered.

The design process for these joints is based on capacity design principles applied at the level of the single joint components. In particular, the dissipative component (i.e. the friction damper) is designed considering the actions at ULS (both seismic and non-seismic load combinations). Conversely, the non-dissipative components are designed starting from the maximum actions transferred by the damper [Francavilla *et al.*, 2020], considering the potential overstrength provided by the friction interface.

Figure 5 – Horizontal (left) and vertical (right) configurations of FREEDAM connections [Francavilla *et al.*, 2020]

The experimental setups employed are shown in Figure 6. Two actuators are used: the first is connected to the beam end to apply the cyclic displacement history; the second is bolted to the column end to apply a constant axial force. Moreover, a restraining system has been used to avoid lateral-torsional buckling of the beams.

Figure 6 – Experimental setup

The cyclic displacements have been imposed according to the AISC 341 protocol, which was applied considering a history of displacements aimed at achieving rotations up to 50 mrad. In Figure 7, the hysteretic curves referring to the horizontal configuration of the FREEDAM connections are shown. It is possible to notice the asymmetry of the moment-rotation response

(a difference of about 30% is observed comparing sagging and hogging bending moments). This behaviour is strictly related to the asymmetric geometry of the connection, and it is due to the asymmetric response of the bottom L-stubs when they are subjected to tension or compression (sagging or hogging bending, respectively). In fact, under tension, the L-stubs exhibit a loss of preload caused by the variability of the pressure on the friction shims.

a) *IPE270 beam and HE220M column* b) *IPE450 beam and HE500B column*
 Figure 7 – Hysteretic curves referring to the horizontal configuration of the FREEDAM joints

Considering the results on the vertical configuration (Figure 8), it is possible to observe a more symmetric behaviour. The slight residual asymmetry is due to the deformability of the angles, which offer a different response in tension and compression. The initial sliding of FREEDAM joints occurs for values of the slip force larger than the one corresponding to the kinematic friction. This behaviour agrees with the experimental results on lap-shear specimens. The initial slip resistance is related to the static value of the friction coefficient, which is higher than the dynamic one, which appears only after a few cycles.

a) *IPE270 beam and HE220M column* b) *IPE450 beam and HE500B column*
 Figure 8 – Hysteretic curves referring to the vertical configuration of the FREEDAM joints

Load cells have been employed to measure the preloading force in the bolts during the tests. The observed loss of preloading was equal to about 20%. At the end of the tests, the friction shims are subjected to some wearing depending on the severity of the loading protocol (Figure 9). Scratches were recognised in the sliding area of the friction shims.

Figure 9 – Nodal components at the end of the tests

4 Pseudo-dynamic testing of a large-scale steel structure equipped with FREEDAM joints

To demonstrate the possibility to realise structures according to the FREEDAM design philosophy, at the STRENGTH (STructural ENgineering Test Hall) laboratory of the University of Salerno, a large-scale (almost real scale) steel structure equipped with FREEDAM connections has been built. The mock-up is characterised by one bay and two storeys (Figure 10): the span is 4 m in the longitudinal direction and 2 m in the transverse direction, while the interstorey height is equal to 2.40 m.

Figure 10 – Tested mock-up (left) and FREEDAM connection (right)

The tested building comprises two Moment Resisting Frames (MRFs) along the longitudinal direction (Figure 11), which withstand the seismic input, while transverse bracings prevent undesired and accidental torsional effects. The rigid decks are made of a corrugated steel sheet HI-BOND A55 with concrete topping. The whole slab has a total height of 100 mm. The floors are disconnected from the primary beams of the MRFs and transfer the loads to five equally spaced secondary beams. IPE 270 and HEB 200 profiles made of S275 and S355 steel grade

have been selected as primary beams and columns, respectively, designed according to Eurocode 8 [CEN, 2019] provisions for DCH (Ductility Class High) buildings, with behaviour factor equal to 6, peak ground acceleration of 0.35g, type-B soil and 1% interstorey drifts under service conditions.

Figure 11 – Longitudinal section of the building mock-up

The seismic response of the mock-up has been assessed by performing five pseudo-dynamic (PsD) tests [Mahin and Shing, 1985], applying the seismic inputs reported in Table 2.

Table 2 – Seismic inputs applied to perform the PsD tests

Test	Station	Date	Natural PGA	PGA for PsD tests
1	Imperial Valley (USA), Agrarias	10/15/1979	0.37 g	1.10 g
2	Spitak (Armenia), Gukasian	12/07/1988	0.20 g	0.80 g
3	Artificial, SIMQKE_GR	-	0.35 g	0.50 g
4	Santa Barbara (USA), Courth	08/13/1978	0.10 g	0.80 g
5	Coalinga (USA), Slack Canyon	05/02/1983	0.17 g	0.80 g

The experimental campaign was interrupted at the 5th test because of a technical problem, consisting of the loss of control of the actuator located at the first level. This induced significant damage to elements connecting the reaction frame to the mock-up.

The main results referred to the global behaviour of the structure are summarised in Table 3 and Figure 12. As it is possible to observe, generally, the higher values of floor displacements and reaction forces of the actuators are achieved for tests 1, 2 and 5, which engaged the structure in the plastic range. Since FREEDAM connections are not conceived with components able to ensure the self-centring of the structure, in tests 1, 2 and 5, residual displacements have been recorded, leading to residual interstorey drifts usually varying between 0.5% and 1%. Instead, the maximum interstorey drifts achieved values higher than 3%, as for the Spitak earthquake.

Table 3 – Global behaviour of the structure

		Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Test 4	Test 5	
Maximum base shear (kN)	Pull	-537	-447	-272	-388	-439	
	Push	477	470	347	483	495	
Peak first floor displacement (mm)	Pull	-73	-53	-41	-56	-72	
	Push	65	79	38	52	61	
Peak roof displacement (mm)	Pull	-104	-84	-75	-89	-112	
	Push	103	112	52	70	85	
Maximum inter-storey drift (%)	Pull	Level 1	-3.0	-2.2	-1.7	-2.3	-3.0
		Level 2	-1.3	-1.3	-1.4	-1.4	-1.7
	Push	Level 1	2.7	3.3	1.6	2.2	2.5
		Level 2	1.6	1.4	0.6	0.7	1.0

Figure 12 – Global behaviour of the structure

The maximum base shear observed was equal to 537 kN, and it was reached during the Imperial Valley seismic input. In contrast, the maximum floor displacements were about 80 mm and 110 mm at the first and second levels, respectively. In Table 4, a summary of the primary response parameters of the FREEDAM connections is reported, for all the tests except Imperial Valley, because of technical issues with the data acquisition system.

As expected, FREEDAM joints have exhibited wide and stable rectangular-shaped hysteretic loops able to dissipate the seismic input energy, limiting the bending moments transmitted to the columns. The maximum joint rotation, equal to 17 mrad, was recorded during Test 2 (Figure 13). It is possible to highlight also the asymmetric behaviour of the connections since the absolute values of the maximum and minimum bending moments are around 90 kNm and 115 kNm, respectively. This agrees with the slight asymmetry already pointed out by the experimental tests on beam-to-column joint sub-assemblies, as discussed in the previous paragraph.

In all the tests, all the structural elements were completely undamaged, highlighting the high performance of the building mock-up and the easy reparability after a sequence of five severe earthquakes.

Table 4 – Local behaviour of connection 1A

Test	Rotation (mrad)	Moment (kNm)		Dissipated energy (kNm)
		Negative	Positive	
1	-	-	-	-
2	17.03	118.36	90.98	4.14
3	3.74	99.24	74.11	0.34
4	4.61	107.55	87.42	2.64
5	12.58	113.82	81.36	5.69

Figure 13 – Local behaviour of FREEDAM connections

5 Specific design rules for FREEDAM frames

Within the FREEDAM and FREEDAM-PLUS project, specific design rules for moment-resisting frames equipped with the new beam-to-column connection typology have been developed. In particular, design rules working within the framework of the draft of the revised version of Eurocode 8 have been developed, using prEN 1998-1-2:2021 [CEN, 2021] as a reference. Even though these rules are in line with the codified recommendations for the

seismic design of steel structures and, therefore, could appear more immediately applicable in everyday design practice, an alternative design procedure, based on the theory of plastic mechanism control (TPMC) [Mazzolani and Piluso, 1997; Montuori et al. 2015], has been also suggested accounting for the specificities of FREEDAM connections. This alternative design procedure has the strong advantage of assuring the prevention of the column yielding and, therefore, perfectly agrees with the free from damage design goal.

5.1 Design rules in line with Eurocode 8

The structures designed according to the code approach in the DC3 ductility class need to respect both local and global hierarchy criteria. The capacity design rule is given by [Piluso et al., 2022]:

$$\sum M_{c.pl.Rd}(N_{Ed}) \geq \sum [\gamma_{rm}\gamma_{sh}M_{f.Rd}] \quad (1)$$

where $\sum M_{c.pl.Rd}(N_{Ed})$ is the sum of the design moment resistances of the column following the EN 1993-1-1:2004, 6.2.9.1 considering the axial load in the seismic design situation and $M_{f.Rd}$ is the sum of the design moments of resistance of the FREEDAM joints. The resistance and stability of non-dissipative members (beams and columns) are checked considering the following internal actions [Piluso et al., 2022]:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{Ed} &= N_{Ed,G} + \gamma_{rm}\gamma_{sh}\Omega_d N_{Ed,E} \\ M_{Ed} &= M_{Ed,G} + \gamma_{rm}\gamma_{sh}\Omega_d M_{Ed,E} \\ V_{Ed} &= V_{Ed,G} + \gamma_{rm}\gamma_{sh}\Omega_d V_{Ed,E} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the material overstrength factor γ_{rm} depends on the randomness of the friction coefficient and the random variability of the tightening torque. It can be assumed equal to $\gamma_{rm} = 1.60$ while the strain hardening parameter γ_{sh} can be assumed as equal to 1. The minimum design overstrength Ω_d is defined as usual:

$$\Omega_d = \min(\Omega_{d,i}) = \min\left(\frac{M_{f.Rd,i} - M_{Ed.G,i}}{M_{Ed,i}}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $M_{f.Rd,i}$ is the design resistance of the FREEDAM connection, $M_{Ed,i}$ is the bending moment resulting from the seismic load combination and $M_{Ed.G,i}$ is the bending moment resulting from the gravity loads included in the seismic load combination.

5.2 Design Procedure according to TPMC

The ‘Theory of Plastic Mechanism Control’ (TPMC), initially proposed by Mazzolani and Piluso (1997) and subsequently update by Montuori et al. (2015), is a useful tool for the seismic design of steel structures. TPMC is based on the kinematic theorem of plastic collapse extended to the concept of equilibrium curve of mechanism. The kinematic theorem of plastic collapse asserts that the collapse multiplier is the minimum among all the kinematically admissible multipliers. Starting from the assumption of a rigid-plastic behaviour, the attention is focused on the structure collapse state. Moreover, according to the TPMC design procedure, second-order effects are directly accounted for by the concept of the equilibrium curve of the mechanism. The unknowns of the design problem are the sections of the columns, on each floor, assuring the desired collapse mechanism while beam sections and/or other dissipative zones are assumed as known quantities and designed to withstand the worst design condition between the fundamental load combination under gravity loads (ULS), the seismic load

combination for serviceability requirements and the seismic load combination for significant damage (SD) (i.e. being the seismic forces scaled down using the q-factor).

TPMC can be properly applied both to structures with traditional connections and structures equipped with FREEDAM connections starting from the same equations with just a few adjustments. It allows the development of the desired global type mechanism (Figure 14), where all the dissipative zones are activated, i.e. the dampers located at the end of the beams and plastic hinges at the base sections of first-storey columns, while all the other columns remain in the elastic range. The beams are designed as non-dissipative members depending on the stresses that FREEDAM connections can transmit. Moreover, they must be designed to withstand also the fundamental load combinations (ULS).

Figure 14 - Collapse mechanisms for the MRFs equipped with FREEDAM connections

The undesired mechanisms for MRFs equipped with FREEDAM connections are depicted in (Figure 14). The solid polygons on the beams represent the FREEDAM dampers actively involved in the kinematic mechanism, and the solid circles on the columns are the plastic hinges involved in the mechanism. In particular, the Type 1 mechanism affects the storeys of the structure starting from the base. The plastic hinges form at the base and top of the involved columns while the friction dampers are activated at the ends of the beams of the storeys involved in the mechanism. Type 2 mechanism starts from the upper storeys of the structure.

The plastic hinges form at the base of the involved columns and the friction dampers are activated at the ends of the beams of the storeys involved in the mechanism. Type 3 mechanism is also called soft-storey mechanism because it involves only one storey. The plastic hinges form at the base and the top of the columns of the same storey.

Among these considered mechanisms the global mechanism is the more dissipative because all the dissipative zones are involved in the mechanism pattern. Moreover, to attain the complete development of the collapse mechanism, plastic hinges at the first-storey column bases are also yielded.

5.2.1 TPMC for DC3 Ductility Class

The structures designed by TPMC in DC3 are aimed to assure a global collapse mechanism (Figure 14). For this reason, all the undesired mechanisms must be avoided. Before the complete development of a kinematic mechanism, significant horizontal displacements arise producing non-negligible second-order effects. Therefore, the kinematic theorem is supported by the concept of the collapse mechanism equilibrium curve [Mazzolani and Piluso, 1997; Piluso, 2015]. Within the kinematic approach, for any given collapse mechanism, the equilibrium curve of the mechanism can be easily obtained by equating the work of the external forces with the internal one due to the plastic hinges involved in the collapse mechanism (being, in the case of FREEDAM connections, the role the plastic moment exerted by the bending moment corresponding to the slippage of the friction dampers). To derive the mechanism equilibrium curve, the second-order work due to the gravity loads has also to be included in the determination of the external work. To this scope, with reference to the k -th storey, the virtual vertical displacements δv_k that occur starting from a deformed configuration defined by the plastic rotation θ and resulting from a virtual plastic rotation $d\theta$ have to be evaluated [Mazzolani and Piluso, 1997; Piluso, 2015] (Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Second-order vertical displacements

In the case of a global mechanism, the work of external forces due to a virtual rotation $d\theta$ of the plastic hinges of the columns, starting from a deformed configuration characterized by a rotation θ of the same columns, is given by the following relation:

$$W_e = \alpha \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k d\theta + \frac{\delta}{h_{n_s}} \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} V_k h_k d\theta \quad (4)$$

The first term of the equation represents the external work due to the seismic horizontal forces, being α the common multiplier, while the second term is the second-order work due to vertical loads, being V_k the total gravity load acting at k -th storey. F_k is the seismic horizontal force applied at the k -th storey and h_k is the distance between the floor level and the foundation. In general, it can be recognized that the vector of vertical virtual displacements has the same shape as the vector of horizontal virtual displacements, being in the case of a global mechanism:

$$\delta v_k = \frac{\delta}{h_{n_s}} h_k d\theta \quad (5)$$

where δ is the top sway displacement.

In the case of a global mechanism the internal work due to the virtual rotation $d\theta$ of the plastic hinges of the columns is:

$$W_i = \left(\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} M_{c.i1} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d.jk} \right) d\theta \quad (6)$$

where $M_{c.ik}$ ($k = 1$) is the plastic moment reduced due to the simultaneous action of the axial force of the i -th column of the k -th storey and $W_{d.jk}$ is the internal work due to the dissipative zones located in j -th bay of k -th storey, to be evaluated depending on the structural typology. By equating the internal with external work the following relation is obtained:

$$\alpha = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.i1} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d.jk}}{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k} - \frac{1}{h_{n_s}} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} V_k h_k}{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k} \delta \quad (7)$$

being n_c the number of columns, n_s the number of storeys and n_b the number of bays.

From this equation it is immediately recognized that the mechanism equilibrium curve is a straight line which can generally be expressed in the following form:

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 - \gamma \delta \quad (8)$$

where α_0 is the kinematically admissible multiplier of the horizontal forces in accordance with the first-order rigid-plastic analysis; γ is the slope of the collapse mechanism equilibrium curve. In the case of a global mechanism the kinematically admissible multiplier of the horizontal forces is:

$$\alpha_0^{(g)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.i1} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d.jk}}{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k} \quad (9)$$

while the slope of the equilibrium curve of the mechanism, $\gamma^{(g)}$, is given by:

$$\gamma^{(g)} = \frac{1}{h_{n_s}} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} V_k h_k}{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k} \quad (10)$$

The parameters of the equilibrium curve of the collapse mechanism for type 1, type 2 and type 3 mechanisms can be easily obtained similarly as follows.

Type 1 Collapse Mechanism

Regarding the i_m -th mechanism of type 1, the kinematically admissible multiplier of horizontal forces is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{0.1}^{(1)} = \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.i1}}{h_1 \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k} & \text{for } i_m = 1 \\ \alpha_{0.i_m}^{(1)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.i1} + \sum_{k=1}^{i_m-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d.jk} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.iim}}{\sum_{k=1}^{i_m} F_k h_k + h_{i_m} \sum_{k=i_m+1}^{i_m} F_k} & \text{for } i_m > 1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

while the slope of the equilibrium curve of the mechanism is given by:

$$\gamma_{i_m}^{(1)} = \frac{1 \sum_{k=1}^{i_m} V_k h_k + h_{i_m} \sum_{k=i_m+1}^{n_s} V_k}{h_{i_m} \sum_{k=1}^{i_m} F_k h_k + h_{i_m} \sum_{k=i_m+1}^{i_m} F_k} \quad (12)$$

Type 2 Collapse Mechanism

Concerning the i_m -th mechanism of type 2, the kinematically admissible multiplier of horizontal forces is given by:

$$\alpha_{0.i_m}^{(2)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.iim} + \sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d.jk}}{\sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k (h_k - h_{i_m-1})} \quad (13)$$

while the slope of the equilibrium curve of the mechanism is:

$$\gamma_{i_m}^{(2)} = \frac{1}{h_{n_s} - h_{i_m-1}} \frac{\sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} V_k (h_k - h_{i_m-1})}{\sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k (h_k - h_{i_m-1})} \quad (14)$$

It is useful to note that, for the $i_m = 1$ equation (13) and (14) coincide, respectively, with equations (9) and (10), because in this case, the mechanism coincides with the global one.

Type 3 Collapse Mechanism

About the i_m -th type 3 mechanism, the kinematically admissible multiplier of horizontal forces is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{0.1}^{(3)} = \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.i1}}{h_1 \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k} & \text{for } i_m = 1 \\ \alpha_{0.i_m}^{(3)} = \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c.iim}}{(h_{i_m} - h_{i_m-1}) \sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k} & \text{for } i_m > 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

while the slope of the equilibrium curve of the mechanism is given by:

$$\gamma_{i_m}^{(3)} = \frac{1}{h_{i_m} - h_{i_m-1}} \frac{\sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} V_k}{\sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k} \quad (16)$$

It is important to emphasize that, for any given geometry of the structural system, the slope of the collapse mechanism equilibrium curve draws its minimum value when the developed collapse mechanism is the global one. According to the kinematic theorem of plastic collapse extended to the concept of mechanism equilibrium curve, the design conditions that must be satisfied to avoid the undesired collapse mechanism require that the equilibrium curve corresponding to the global mechanism must be located below those corresponding to the

undesired mechanisms up to a top sway maximum displacement, δ_u , compatible with the local ductility resources of the structure (Figure 16).

Figure 16 - Design statement of TPMC

With these conditions, we are imposing that, within the whole design displacement range, the collapse multiplier corresponding to the global mechanism is the smallest among all the kinematically admissible multipliers. Then the global mechanism is the only mechanism that can develop. The representation reported in Figure 16 can be translated into the following inequalities:

$$\alpha_0^{(g)} - \gamma^{(g)} \delta_u \leq \alpha_{i_m}^{(t)} - \gamma_{i_m}^{(t)} \delta_u \quad \text{for} \quad \begin{cases} i_m = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \\ t = 1, 2, 3 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Eq. (17) constitutes the TPMC statement [Piluso, 2015] and it is valid independently of the structural typology.

The internal work $W_{d,jk}$, for a unit value of the virtual plastic rotation, due to the dissipative zones of j -th bay of k -th storey has to be computed accounting for the actual flexural resistance of dissipative zones. In particular:

$$W_{d,jk} = 2 \gamma M_{f.Rd.jk} \frac{L_j}{L_{j,k}^*} \quad (18)$$

where:

- $\gamma = \gamma_{rm} \cdot \gamma_{sh}$ is the overstrength factor accounting for the random variability of the material properties and the strain-hardening;
- $\gamma_{rm}=1.6$, in the case of FREEDAM connections, is the overstrength factor of the friction coefficient (i.e. the second principle of capacity design is applied);
- $\gamma_{sh}=1$, in the case of FREEDAM connections, because no hardening occurs;
- L_j is the j -th bay length (i.e. the bay span between the columns' axes)
- $L_{j,k}^*$ represents, regarding the k -th storey, the actual length of the j -th bay span (i.e. the distance between the flanges of two adjacent columns)
- $M_{f.Rd.jk}$ is the slippage bending moment of the beam-to-column connection equipped with the friction damper (j -th beam, k -th storey).

Columns design algorithm

The column sections needed to prevent undesired collapse mechanisms can be derived using the following design procedure being known all the dissipative zones.

- a) Selection of the top sway displacement, $\delta_u = \theta_{pl} \cdot h_{ns}$
 - θ_{pl} is the beams plastic rotation, assumed equal to 0,04 rad
 - h_{ns} is the total height of the structure.
- b) Computation of the slope of mechanism equilibrium curves $\gamma_{im}^{(t)}$ employing equations (12), (14) and (16). From Eq. (10) we obtain the slope of the equilibrium curve of the global mechanism $\gamma^{(g)}$ which is the minimum among the values of $\gamma_{im}^{(t)}$.
- c) Design of the first storey columns sections.

When $i_m = 1$ the inequality (17) is reduced to a single design condition needed to avoid the soft-storey mechanism at the first storey:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,i.1} \geq \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d,jk} + (\gamma_1^{(3)} - \gamma^{(g)}) \delta_u \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k}{2 \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k h_k}{h_1 \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} F_k} - 1} \quad (19)$$

- d) Computation of the axial load acting in the columns at collapse state i.e., when the global mechanism is fully developed.

The sum of the plastic moments required at the first storey (Eq. (19)) is spread among all the columns. By knowing the internal design actions, the sections of the columns can be designed by choosing the appropriate profiles from standard shapes. From this design, it is possible to obtain the final value of the sum of the plastic moments of the columns at the first storey, $\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,i.1}^*$.

- e) Computation of the sum of plastic moment of columns, reduced to the contemporary action of the axial load required at each storey to avoid undesired mechanism by the following conditions:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(1)} \geq (\alpha^{(g)} + \gamma_{i_m}^{(1)} \delta_u) \left(\sum_{k=1}^{i_m} F_k h_k + h_{i_m} \sum_{k=i_m+1}^{i_m} F_k \right) - \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,i.1}^* - \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d,jk} \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(2)} \geq (\alpha^{(g)} + \gamma_{i_m}^{(2)} \delta_u) - \sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k (h_k - h_{i_m-1}) - \sum_{k=1}^{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} W_{d,jk} \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(3)} \geq (\alpha^{(g)} + \gamma_{i_m}^{(3)} \delta_u) \frac{(h_{i_m} - h_{i_m-1})}{2} \sum_{k=i_m}^{n_s} F_k \quad (22)$$

It is important to underline that $\alpha^{(g)}$ is computed by Eq. (8) by replacing $\sum_{k=1}^{n_c} M_{c.1}$ with $\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,i.1}^*$ in Eq.(9).

- f) Selection of the maximum design value of the sum of the plastic moments of the columns as the maximum among the values provided by Eqs. (20) to (22).

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m} \geq \max \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(1)} ; \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(2)} ; \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} M_{c,ii_m}^{(3)} \right\} \quad (23)$$

- g) The sum of plastic moment of the columns, reduced by the simultaneous action of the axial load, at each storey (for $i_m > 1$) given by Eq. (23), has to be distributed among the different storey columns to obtain the values of M_{c,ii_m} .

- h) According to a technological condition, if needed, it is imposed that, starting from the base, the column sections cannot increase along with the height of the building. If this condition is not satisfied the procedure must be repeated from point e) because the first-storey column sections have to be properly modified.
- i) Finally, if the structure exhibits a collapse mechanism of global type but does not satisfy the drift limitation provided by the code recommendations, it is suggested to increase the beams sections and repeat the procedure. This necessarily leads to an increase in the columns sections and, consequently, to an increase in the lateral stiffness of the structure.

Despite regarding moment-resisting frames with traditional beam-to-column connections, additional information about the use of the theory of plastic mechanism control can be obtained in [Montuori *et al.*, 2015], where also a worked numerical example is provided. A numerical example dealing with connections equipped with friction dampers is reported in [Piluso *et al.*, 2022]

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CONNESSIONI FREEDAM: PROGETTAZIONE, SPERIMENTAZIONE E COMPORTAMENTO SOTTO AZIONI SISMICHE

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SOMMARIO: Questo articolo è dedicato ad una breve presentazione dei principali risultati ottenuti nell'ambito del progetto di ricerca FREEDAM. Il progetto è stato completato e, di recente, anche la divulgazione dei risultati è giunta al traguardo. Il progetto è stato dedicato allo sviluppo di connessioni trave-colonna a basso danneggiamento basate sull'utilizzo di dissipatori ad attrito concepiti per sostituire le tradizionali zone dissipative dei telai con giunti resistenti a flessione, ossia le estremità delle travi. Viene presentata la concezione di queste connessioni innovative e vengono riassunte le prove sperimentali, svolte presso l'Università degli Studi di Salerno durante il progetto FREEDAM, riguardanti i dissipatori ad attrito, i sottoassemblaggi nodali trave-colonna e la simulazione sismica in una scala reale di un edificio ad una campata e due piani con il metodo di prova pseudodinamico. Infine, vengono presentate nel quadro dell'Eurocodice 8 e secondo la TPMC le procedure di progettazione per telai sismo-resistenti in acciaio dotati di tali connessioni.

PAROLE CHIAVE: dissipatori ad attrito, collegamenti trave-colonna, strutture a basso danneggiamento, strutture in acciaio, controllo del collasso